

STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES AFTER SCHOOL CLOSURE DUE TO PANDEMIC

Analyn D. Sillacay, M.A. Ed.

analynsillacay@fcic.edu.ph

M.A.Ed. Major in Educational Management

Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception

Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines

Ma. Victoria Gonzaga, EdD.

mavictoriagonzaga@fcic.edu.ph

Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception

Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines

 Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Insights is a peer-reviewed academic journal that prioritizes the development of knowledge in multidisciplinary educational research. With a broad scope, the journal aims to disseminate information and provide a forum for discussion, theoretical inquiry, practical applications, research discoveries, and experimentations in the field of education. FCIC Insights is maintained and supervised by Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay, Leyte, Incorporated.

Recommended Citation:

Sillacay, A. D., and Gonzaga, M. V. (2023). Students' Engagement in Face-to-Face Classes After School Closure Due to Pandemic. *Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Insights*. 1-13.

STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES AFTER SCHOOL CLOSURE DUE TO PANDEMIC

Analyn D. Sillacay, M.A. Ed.¹, Ma. Victoria Gonzaga, Ed.D.²

^{1,2}Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception
Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines
analynsillacay@fcic.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

This research aimed to determine the level of Students' Engagement in terms of Behavioral, Cognitive, and Affective Engagement in Damulaan National High School-Senior High School. This also focuses on the Socio-Demographic profile of the respondents according to age, sex, and parent's monthly income, and relationship to students' level of academic achievement. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square test and One-way Anova to determine the significant difference between the areas of student engagement and socio-demographic profile, while a correlation method to determine the significant relationship of students' engagement and academic performance. The study showed that most of the respondent were females and majority belong to poverty level with an income of below 5,000.00. Moreover, results revealed that the respondents are "High Engaged" in Behavioral engagement, while Cognitive, and Affective engagement belongs to "Fairly Engage" which means less engaged in various class activities. The academic performance of the respondent's got a Satisfactory rating with a grading scale of (80-84). Furthermore, there is a significant difference between each level of engagement. While, for the significant difference of Socio Demographic profile and student engagement it was found out that there was no significant among Sex, and Family income, however Age and Affective engagement has a significant difference. Lastly, the relationship between students' academic achievement and the level of student engagement has no significant relationship which means they are not connected to one another.

Keywords: *Student engagement, behavioral, cognitive, and affective level of engagement, academic performance.*

Received: February, 2023

Accepted: March, 2023

Available: May, 2023

INTRODUCTION

Student engagement refers to the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion that students show when they are learning or being taught in school, which it extends to the level of motivation they must learn and progress in their education Saeedi, Ghafouri, Tehrani & Abedini (2021). In particular, students' participation in learning is acknowledged, and it may be broken down into three dimensions: behavioral engagement, cognitive engagement, and emotional engagement Nguyen, Cannata, & Miller (2018).

The limited face to face classes in the Philippine particularly in the Educational system reopen schools' campuses. For many, this is a return to normality (Carpena, 2022). Thus, DepEd Order No. 34 S.2022 sets the start of classes on August 22 and end on July 7, 2023. It states to re-open schools and implement five days of in-person classes will be required, pre-pandemic regulatory permits and licenses, as required by law and regulations. For the two years of modular classes, public and private schools were filled once again with students, teachers, administrators and persons involved. (Mingoy, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Damulaan Senior High School is under the Department of Education in Leyte Division implemented the limited face to face classes, one of the concerns and challenges of the school is the problem of students' academic performance after the two years of pandemic. Thus, the School's development program according to DepEd No. 001 (2020) includes initiatives like teacher training to improve learning pathways and close collaboration with schools to improve how information is given and retained.

The study was conducted in Damulaan National High School-Senior High School, which is located in Damulaan, one of the 20 barangays of Albuera in the Province of Leyte. The barangay is home to both an elementary and secondary school. The school is under the jurisdiction of the Department of Education - Leyte Division, Philippines, and is one of the many schools in the division located in Leyte. The Senior High School offers HUMSS and TVL strand and has total number of 236 enrollees and used complete enumeration of Grade 11 and Grade 12 students Senior High School.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Name of School	Number of Students		Total
	Male	Female	
Grade 11			
Hyacinth	12	22	34
Lily	14	19	33
Orchid	27	15	42
Rose	22	17	39
Grade 12			
Cherry	9	17	26
Peach	10	18	28
Melon	15	19	34
Grand Total	109	127	236

Research Instrument

This study used and adopted the Student Engagement tool from the Dr. Delfino (2018). Author's consent was sought on the use of the tool, consent is attached in Appendix A. In getting the General Point average of learners' GPA standard category in the Department of Education was used in the study.

The research used quantitative research utilizing a descriptive correlational design to determine Senior High School students' engagement in the face-to-face classes after school closure due to Pandemic. For the significant difference among the level of students' engagement in the area of Cognitive, Affective, and Behavioral, and in getting the significant difference of Socio Demographic Profile in terms of sex, and parents' monthly income of students a Chi square was used. Chi-square test is used to assess the degree between variables when comparing from a random sample in order to check if there is goodness of fit between expected and observed results. (Hayes, 2022)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. The Demographic profile of the Senior High School students of Damulaan National High School – SHS, Albuera, Leyte.

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (in Years)		
15-16	43	18.7%
17 -18	156	67.8%
19-20	24	10.4%
21-22	6	2.6%
23 and above	2	.43%
Total	230	100
Sex		
Male	103	44.59%
Female	128	55.41%
Total	231	100
Parents' Monthly Income		
Below Php 5,000.00	169	73.1%
Php 5,000.00 – 10,000.00	29	12.5%
Php 10,000.00 – Php 15,000.00	14	6.1%
Php 15,000.00 – 20,000.00	3	1.3%
Php 30,000.00 – 35,000.00	3	1.3%
Above Php 35,000.00	0	0%
Not Indicated	13	5.6%
Total	223	100%

Age. The majority of the respondents belong to the age range of 17-18 years old, with 156 (67.8%) in the adolescent stage category. This finding is significant as these learners represent the target population of interest, especially given the age requirement for Senior High School as specified by the Department of Education. The lowest age bracket among the respondents falls under the range of 21-22 years old. This implies that is important number of learners belong to the Balik Aral program, ALS and learners who chose to return to school after stopping their education due to the school closure brought about by the pandemic, as indicated by the Learners Information System (LIS) in 2022.

Sex. The distribution of respondents based on sex was also observed. The data shows that there are more female students, a total of one hundred twenty-eight (55.41%) while males are only one hundred three (44.59%). The data collected in this study are also congruent with the age data recorded in the Learner Information System (LIS) from August to December 2022. Additionally, the finding that female students comprise the majority of the respondents in this study because the larger population are female learners enrolled in Damulaan Senior High School, Albueria, Leyte.

This is reliable with previous studies that emphasized the gender gap in enrollment across various levels of education in the Philippines, including primary, secondary, and tertiary education. (de Guzman, Caluya, Ramos & Padua 2018).

Parents Family income. Majority of the respondents belong to the low-income family with a monthly family income of 5,000.00 and below (poverty level). Households falling under this income bracket have the lowest income rates and regularly struggle to meet basic food and non-food necessity, living in poverty may not have access to adequate healthcare, education, or other essential resources (PSA 2018).

Level of Student Engagement

Behavioral Engagement

This type of engagement is all about how engaged and willing the pupils are to take part in the activities in the classroom (McCrary, Levine, Hunt, Hilliard & Lockett, 2019).

Table 3.1 Distribution of Students' level on Behavioral Engagement

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Level of Engagement
1. I come to class every day.	3.42	EE
2. I have fun in class.	3.16	HE
3. I am confident that I can learn and do well in the class.	3.00	HE
4. I participate actively in small group discussion.	2.83	HE
5. I am staying up on the readings.	2.74	HE
6. I make sure to study on a regular basis.	2.76	HE
7. I take good notes in class.	2.67	HE
8. I am doing well on the tests.	2.59	FE
9. I am getting a good grade.	2.47	FE
10. I asked questions in class or contribute to class discussions.	2.42	FE
11. I come to class without completing readings or assignments.	2.23	FE
Overall	2.75	HE

Legend:

- 3.4 - 4.0 *Extremely Engaged (EE)* - This means that students are extremely well engaged in various class activities.
- 2.6 - 3.3 *Highly Engaged (HE)* - This means that students are highly engaged various class activities.
- 1.8 - 2.5 *Fairly Engaged (FE)* - This means that students are less engaged in various class activities.
- 1.0- 1.7 *Not Engaged (NE)* - This means that students are not engaged in various class activities.

Table 3.1 presents the result and the indicator with the highest mean of 3.42 with the statement "*I come to class every day.*" Despite the challenges that learners face related to their living conditions and their parents' monthly income of below 5,000.00, it is still clear that the majority of learners show a high level of attendance, with a significant number coming to class every day. This finding is consistent as shown in the School Form 2 (SF2), which refers to the "Daily Attendance Report", a tool used for tracking the attendance of learners.

The study shows that on the Behavioral Engagement the respondents were highly involved in learning, as presented with the overall weighted mean of 2.75. This score falls into "*Highly Engaged.*" which indicates that the majority of learners are actively participating in various class activities.

Cognitive Engagement

Table 3.2 Distribution of Students' level on Behavioral Engagement

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Level of Engagement
1. I used an electronic medium (Facebook, chat group, internet, instant messaging, etc.) to discuss or complete an assignment.	2.78	FE
2. I am finding ways to make the course material relevant to my life	2.70	HE
3. I prepared two or more drafts of a paper or assignment before Submitting it to the instructor/professor.	2.46	FE
4. I put together ideas or concepts from different courses when completing assignment or during class discussion.	2.45	FE
5. I worked on a paper or project that required integrating ideas or Information from various sources.	2.43	FE
6. I made a class presentation for specific topic.	2.41	FE
7. I worked harder that you thought you could meet an instructor's standards or expectations.	2.39	FE
8. I am looking over class notes between classes to make sure I understand the materials	2.39	FE
9. I discussed ideas from your readings or classes with other outside of class (students, family members, co-workers, etc.)	2.39	FE
10. I find ways to make the course interesting to me	2.35	FE
11. I think about the course between class meetings.	2.19	FE
12. I discussed ideas from your readings or classes with faculty members outside of class	2.15	FE
13. I am applying course materials to my life.	2.13	FE
14. I used e-mail to communicate with an instructor.	2.01	FE
15. I discussed grades or assignments with an instructor.	1.9	FE
16. I go to the professor's office hours to review assignments of test, or to ask questions.	1.82	FE

Overall	2.31	FE
----------------	-------------	-----------

Legend:

- 3.4 - 4.0 *Extremely Engaged (EE)* - This means that students are extremely well engaged in various class activities.
- 2.6 - 3.3 *Highly Engaged (HE)* - This means that students are highly engaged various class activities.
- 1.8 - 2.5 *Fairly Engaged (FE)* - This means that students are less engaged in various class activities.
- 1.0 - 1.7 *Not Engaged (NE)* - This means that students are not engaged in various class activities.

As shown in Table 3.2 it appears that the majority of the respondents in the survey chose “I used an electronic medium (Facebook, chat group, internet, instant messaging, etc.) to discuss or complete an assignment” with a mean score of 2.78. This indicates that students are taking an active role in their learning process that students are highly engaged in various class activities by using of technology, and the internet. However, the low indicator is “I go to the professor’s office hours to review assignments of test, or to ask questions, one reason is that students are more comfortable communicating through electronic media that can provide information and make it easier for students to ask questions and express concerns without feeling embarrassed or judged likewise, students may be hesitant to go to office hours because they feel that it is a sign of weakness for not understanding the material. This result is reliable and related to a low level of engagement in affective as reflected in Table 3.3 specifically to work with faculty members on activities.

Affective Engagement

Table 3.3 Distribution of Students’ level on Affective Engagement

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level Engagement
1. I had serious conversation with students who are very different from me in terms if their religious belief, political opinions, or personal values.	2.62	FE
2. I include diverse perspective (different races, religion, genders, political beliefs, etc.) in class discussions or writing assignment.	2.49	FE
3. I worked with other students on projects during class	2.46	FE
4. I worked with classmates outside of class to prepare class assignments	2.22	FE
5. I tutored or taught other students (paid or voluntary)	2.13	FE
6. I participated in a community-based project (e.g., service learning) as part of a regular course	2.12	FE
7. I talked about career plans with a faculty member or adviser	2.12	FE
8. I worked with faculty members on activities other than coursework (committees, orientation, student’s life activities, etc.)	2.10	FE
Overall	2.28	FE

Table 3.3 shows that the highest indicator for affective engagement is " I had serious conversation with students who are very different from me in terms of their religious belief, political opinions, or personal values.," which falls under the Highly Engaged category. This means that students in senior high school, who are typically between 16 and 18 years old, are actively seeking out opportunities to engage in discussions with peers who hold different perspectives.

The data show that the lowest indicator for affective engagement is “*I worked with faculty members on activities other than coursework (committees, orientation, student’s life activities, etc.)*”, which received a mean of 2.10, indicating a fairly low level of engagement. This finding is similar to the results of cognitive engagement, where the lowest mean score was reported for the activity of “going to professor”. These results suggest that students may not be fully utilizing the opportunities to engage with faculty members beyond their coursework, which may have implications for their overall academic and personal growth.

Students’ Academic Performance

Table 4. Academic Performance of the students

Grade Point Average (GPA)		Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	(90-100)	24	10.16%
Very Satisfactory	(89-85)	67	28.38%
Satisfactory	(80-84)	89	37.71%
Fairly Satisfactory	(79-75)	49	20.44%
Did Not Meet Expectation	(75 below	7	2.97%
MEAN		236	100%

Table 4 displays the distribution of academic performance of the respondents during their first semester grades for all Grade 11 and 12 students in academic year 2022-2023. Based on the data, the highest percentage of students (37.71%) obtained a Satisfactory level rating of (80-84). This indicates that the student's performance meets the minimum requirements for the subject and may have a basic understanding of the concepts taught.

The "Fairly Satisfactory" category represents approximately 20.44% of the total scores. This indicates that while these scores may not be as high as the other categories, it represents a significant portion of the total scores in the study and highlights the need for support and continuous evaluation to ensure that all students can achieve their learning goals. As a result, made in the previous paragraph, it is necessary to fully understand issues on this engagement.

Differences between Socio Demographic Profile and the Level of Engagement.

The results of the significant difference in students’ level of engagement in the areas of cognitive, behavioral, and affective engagement and students Socio Demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and parent’s family income are presented in this section. Table 5 uses Chi-square test of significant, while Table 5.1 on age uses Analysis of variance because the method is used to compare the means of three or more groups to determine if there are significant differences between them.

Table 5.1 Differences among the Level of Student engagement across Sex and Family Income of the students

Level of Engagement	Socio-demographic Profile	Chi-Square Value	Df	p-value	Significance
Behavioral	Sex	2.676	2	.262	Not Significant
	Family Income	10.483	10	.399	Not Significant
Cognitive	Sex	.839	2	.657	Not Significant
	Family Income	7.872	10	.641	Not Significant
Affective	Sex	5.934	3	.115	Not Significant
	Family Income	9.724	15	.837	Not Significant

A socio-demographic profile contains crucial details in the senior high school students. Age, Gender, and parent’s monthly income are the components and can have an impact on many other areas of the level of engagement.

Table 5.2 Differences among the levels of student engagement across ages

Socio-demographic Profile	Level of Engagement	F-computed	Df	p-value	Significance
Age	Behavioral	.859	2	.425	Not Significant
	Cognitive	2.742	2	.067	Not Significant
	Affective	3.041	3	.030	Significant

Age. This study used the statistical test known as one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to examine the relationship between age and the level of engagement namely Behavioral, Cognitive and Affective engagement. The results of the ANOVA test indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean age of the various levels in Behavioral and Cognitive engagement. This indicates that respondents' levels of engagement were the same age groups which further explains that the engagement of the respondents' of students ages did not make a difference in their level of engagement on how engaged they are in class, that the majority of the mean scores were above 17, which indicates that the respondents generally had the same level of engagement, regardless of their age, These data suggest that the level of engagement may not be significantly influenced by age.

The overall finding on this test is that Socio-demographic profile particularly in sex, and parent’s monthly income is not a strong effect of students learning styles. It is crucial to remember that just because there is no connection and relationship between two variables, it does not always follow that there is no connection at all, because even though it does not discover a significant relationship this does not suggest that gender has no bearing on how students choose to learn in class activities. According to Cocea, Weibelzahl, & Stathopoulou, (2019) concluded that socio demographic features were not significant indicators of engagement, the prior knowledge and personal interest were other factors also.

Moreover, Sun, Lin, & Zheng (2018) revealed no evidence of a significant link between parental education level, occupation, or family income and their children's academic involvement in learning environment. According to these results, parental socio-demographic

characteristics may have some bearing on how academically engaged their children are, but they may not be the only or even the most significant ones.

Significant Difference among the Level of Student Engagement in the areas of Cognitive, Behavioral, and Affective Engagement.

This section presents the result of the significant difference among the level of Student Engagement in the areas of Cognitive, Behavioral, and Affective Engagement. The data below were both tested using the Chi-square test of significance utilizing both the critical value test and the p-value test at 0.5 significance level.

Table 6. Significance Difference among the Level of Student Engagement in the areas of Cognitive, Behavioral, and Affective Engagement

Level of Engagement	Chi Square Computed	df	p- value	Significance
<i>Behavioral</i>	132.260	2	.000	<i>Significant</i>
<i>Cognitive</i>	103.97	2	.000	<i>Significant</i>
<i>Affective</i>	133.83	3	.000	<i>Significant</i>
Overall	154.086	6	.000	Significant

Significant difference between each level of behavioral engagement across different groups, indicate that the groups differ in their engagement in the behavioral aspect of the study. Similarly, there is a significant difference in the level of cognitive engagement among different groups of students, suggesting that the groups vary in their engagement in cognitive aspect. The chi-square test results reveal a significant difference in affective engagement among different student groups, indicating that the groups differ in their emotional engagement of the study.

Overall, the assessment of engagement levels across the three domains of cognitive, affective, and behavioral indicates a significant difference among the responses of the student to various groups. This implies that the degree of engagement between each level of students is not the same, suggesting that some students may be more engaged in the cognitive, affective, or behavioral aspects of their studies compared to others.

This imply that it is useful for developing interventions or strategies to improve student engagement in specific domains, and to identify factors that are associated with higher levels of engagement with different groups of students.

Significant Relationship between the students' level of Academic Achievement and the Level of Student Engagement.

This presents the result of the significant relationship on Students academic performance in the academic year 2022-2023 and the level of student engagement, the table below use Correlational method in Spearman Matrix.

Table 7. Relationship between the students' level of Academic Achievement and the Level of Student Engagement

Level	N	Correlation Coefficient	Relationship	p-value	Significant	
Academic Achievement	Behavioral	231	-.065	Negligible relationship	.325	Not Significant
	Cognitive	231	-.022	Negligible relationship	.745	Not Significant
	Affective	231	.062	Slight relationship	.348	Not Significant

The data was analyzed using a correlational study to investigate the relationship between academic performance and levels of student engagement in behavioral, affective, and cognitive domains. The results, presented in the form of a correlation matrix (Spearman's correlation), indicate that there is no significant relationship of academic performance and student engagement. Furthermore, it also points the idea that the relationship between student's engagement and academic achievement of the student remain complicated issues, including school culture and its environment, teachers practices in class and methods, as well as students background.

The findings could have several implications for educators and policy maker, it suggests that educators and school administrators need to recognized the value of student engagement while also ensuring that academic performance is not compromised. Finding a balance between academic and extracurricular commitments can help student achieve their academic and personal goals while fostering a positive and supportive leaning environment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based from the results, it is concluded that there is a gender disparity in the enrollment patterns of senior high school tracks in Damulaan National High School – Senior High School. Majority of the responses are in the poor family income, but despite having a low-income status of parents, students are willing to come based on the result on Behavioral engagement presented. There is a low engagement in both Cognitive and Affective engagement, it was discovered that students are less engaged in various class activities and in their emotional states and interest in school activities. The general pattern indicates that students are not as interested to engage in academic work, despites differences of student's response.

REFERENCES

- Cocca, M., Weibelzahl, S., & Stathopoulou, A. (2019). Identifying factors influencing affective engagement in MOOCs. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 12(1), 63-75. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2018.2875609>
- de Guzman, M. R. T., Caluya, G. F., Ramos, R. G., & Padua, R. A. (2018). Factors affecting academic performance of undergraduate students: A case study of the students of the University of the Philippines Visayas. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1049(1), 012026. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1049/1/012026
- DepEd Order No. 34, s. 2022. (2022). Guidelines on the conduct of Remedial, Advancement, and Enrichment Classes During Summer 2022 in Light of the Ongoing COVID-19 Public Health Emergency. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/DO_s2022_034.pdf
- Delfino, A. P. (2019). Student engagement and academic performance of students of Partido State University. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 15(1), 22–41. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v15i3.05>
- Fredricks, J.A. (2022). The Measurement of Student Engagement: Methodological Advances and Comparison of New Self-report Instruments. In: Reschly, A.L., Christenson, S.L. (eds) *Handbook of Research on Student Engagement*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-07853-8_29
- Hartono, F. P., Sumarno, N. U., & Puji, R. P. N. (2019). The level of student engagement based on gender and grade on history subject of senior high school students in jember regency. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(8), 21–26.
- Kurtz, H., Lloyd, S., Harwin, A., Chen, V., & Furuya, Y. (2021). Student Mental Health during the Pandemic: Educator and Teen Perspectives. *Editorial Projects in Education*. <https://www.mendeley.com/catalogue/37dc68a9-bb19-3073-85c9-6e46efb2e75f/>
- Mingoy, G. (2022). Philippines once again filled with students. *The Philippine Star*. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/education/2022/06/08/2199826/philippines-once-again-filled-students>
- Nguyen, T. D., Cannata, M., & Miller, J. (2018). Understanding student behavioral engagement: Importance of student interaction with peers and teachers. *Journal of Educational Research*, 111(2), 163–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2016.1220359>
- Philippines Department of Education. (2020). Guidelines for the conduct of off-campus activities during the COVID-19 outbreak (DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2020) [PDF file]. Retrieved from http://deped.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2020/03/DM_s2020_001.pdf

Saeedi M, Ghafouri R, Tehrani FJ, Abedini Z. (2021) The effects of teaching methods on academic motivation in nursing students: A systematic review. *J Educ Health Promot.* 10:271. doi: 10.4103/jehp.jehp_1070_20. PMID: 34485568; PMCID: PMC8396058.

Sun, Y., Liu, R. D., Oei, T. P., Zhen, R., Ding, Y., & Jiang, R. (2020). Perceived parental warmth and adolescents' math engagement in China: The mediating roles of need satisfaction and math self-efficacy. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2020.101837>

